

Between Wenzel and Cassie: The life of water at tailored silica bubble interfaces

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GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Hypothesis: The behavior of water confined at the surface of particles adsorbed at interfaces plays a critical role in the stability and functionality of Pickering systems such as silica-stabilized microbubbles. Changes in the hydrophobicity of the adsorbed silica particles are expected to influence the macroscopic stability of these systems. We hypothesized that the high incoherent neutron cross-section of hydrogen can be exploited to distinguish differences in wetting behavior between these systems.

Experiments: Microbubbles stabilized by silica nanoparticles with varying degrees of surface hydrophobicity were formulated to test this hypothesis. Micropipette aspiration of the microbubbles was used to confirm the air-in-water structure. Using a combination of three neutron spectrometers the dynamics of water at the interface of these Pickering-stabilized structures was studied. The resulting water mobility was interpreted based on their surface chemistry.

Findings: Hydrophilic silica particles promoted a Wenzel-like wetting state, characterized by increased solid-water contact and reduced water mobility. In contrast, hydrophobic particles resulted in a configuration like the Cassie-Baxter state with entrapped air pockets, leading to enhanced water mobility and bulk-like behavior. These changes were associated with nanoscale surface interactions. These findings indicate that neutron spectroscopy

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provides a new method to determine the wetting of interfacially adsorbed Pickering particles in situ and therewith can help to better formulate Pickering systems.

1. Introduction

Colloidal systems stabilized by Pickering particles, defined as solid particles adsorbed in a liquid-liquid interface, are extensively studied due to their remarkable stability and tunability. These particles are also studied for applications in food encapsulation and controlled release [1–3]. However, in 2017 the Royal Society of Chemistry organized a workshop motivated by the observation that ‘*Despite being recognised for more than a century, Pickering stabilization has received relatively little commercial attention*’. One of the conclusions of the workshop was that application of Pickering-stabilized systems is hampered by a lack of practical formulation guidelines. Conventional surfactants are generally characterized by parameters such as their hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) value that guide the formulator on how to use these surfactants. For Pickering stabilizers such information is still lacking. Additionally, the in situ determination of the contact angle of the particles at interfaces, one of the most important parameters determining the functioning of Pickering stabilizers, is very difficult to obtain [4]. A review in 2023 therefore still concluded that ‘*Particle adsorption at the two-phase interface determines the stability of Pickering emulsions. Consequently, the emphasis should be on the interfacial characteristics of Pickering emulsions*’ and that existing methods for the interfacial characterization of Pickering emulsions, ‘*have not been further developed or perfected for studying emulsions in the past decade*’ [5]. Given the pronounced structural perturbations of water near solid interfaces, parameters such as the diffusion coefficient and the ratio of immobile to mobile protons can be quantitatively correlated with surface chemical characteristics [6]. This motivated our investigation using neutron spectroscopy, a technique well-suited for probing interfacial water dynamics due to the charge neutrality of neutrons and the high incoherent scattering cross-section of hydrogen atoms. These properties enable in situ characterization of water behavior at the surface of Pickering particles. The diffusion coefficients obtained from such analyses may provide indirect insights into the Gibbs free energy near the interfaces, which can be further correlated with macroscopic interfacial properties such as the contact angle [7–9].

To test our hypothesis, we investigated microbubbles stabilized by silica nanoparticles as a Pickering-stabilized system [10]. These gas-filled spheres, which are surrounded by a liquid phase, can be synthesized by utilizing commercially available fumed silica particles (FSPs) with tailored wettability [11–15]. Utilizing micropipette aspiration technique, we demonstrate that the Bubbles can burst during aspiration, confirming the formation of a dense silica layer (shell) at the air-water interface [16]. Surface functionalization, achieved by reducing the concentration of surface silanol groups ($-\text{SiOH}$), lowers the surface energy and surface charge density, thereby enhancing particle hydrophobicity. These modifications influence water adsorption capacity and may alter ionic strength, ultimately affecting the overall colloid stability. In these systems, interfacial phenomena, including thermal properties, particle size, surface charge, as well as the dynamics of water within the interfaces, are expected to play a crucial role in encapsulation efficiency, stability and diffusivity in aqueous environments [8,17–22].

From a theoretical perspective, wettability at solid-liquid interfaces is commonly described by the Wenzel and Cassie-Baxter states [23–25] (Fig. 1). In the Wenzel state, the liquid fully penetrates the surface roughness, maximizing the solid-liquid contact area. This configuration typically results in enhanced adhesion between the liquid and the solid, promoting stronger molecular interactions such as hydrogen bonding. As a result, water at such surfaces in the Wenzel state generally exhibit reduced molecular mobility, which results in a smaller diffusion coefficient, and increased interfacial adhesion. In contrast, the Cassie-Baxter

state describes partial wetting of the solid surface, with air pockets trapped beneath the liquid. This configuration greatly reduces the direct interaction between the solid and the liquid. This leads to weaker molecular adhesion and minimized interactions, resulting in higher molecular mobility due to minimal direct contact with the solid interface. This implies that water on a Cassie-Baxter surface is only loosely associated with the interface without a continuous bound water layer [26,27]. In fully aqueous environments, hydrophobic surfaces can cause water molecules to arrange into low entropy, like “cages” around the hydrophobic groups (often described as a structurally ordered hydration shell) [28], while hydrophilic surfaces behave quite differently. In fact, these surfaces interact favorably with the water molecules through hydrogen bonding or dipole interactions. However, in a predominantly dry or powdered system like the microbubbles studied here, water does not form a stable hydration shell around hydrophobic regions; instead, it tends to avoid direct contact with the hydrophobic surface altogether. Thus, in the context of this study, a Cassie-Baxter wetting regime means that very little water remains directly at the silica interface; any water present is unconfined and should retain a more bulk-like character, moving freely or residing elsewhere in the matrix. In effect, the hydrophobic interface is “rigid” in the sense that water does not wet or soften it, while the few water molecules that are present are highly mobile. On the contrary, we hypothesize that hydrophilic surfaces in the Wenzel state can still retain a small amount of strongly bound water that is adsorbed onto the surface even at low humidity.

To experimentally validate this framework, we employed inelastic neutron scattering (INS) to capture vibrational dynamics related directly to hydrogen bonding strength and molecular rigidity on the femto-second time scale (fs). At picosecond and nanosecond time scales (ps and ns), slower relaxation processes, seeing as a broadening in the energy spectrum at the energy equals zero, i.e. the elastic line, can be detected. This spectral response is called quasielastic neutron scattering (QENS) and allows detailed investigations into molecular diffusion, rotational mobility, and hydrogen bond rearrangements. Evaluation of the evolution of the quasielastic (QE) response as a function of the momentum transfer allows for such analysis. As the structure of water is perturbed heavily near surfaces, affecting water diffusion, a clear relationship between the variation of the diffusion coefficient, D , and surface properties, [6] can be obtained. Moreover, localized vibrational motions, such as the Boson peak (Bp), were also probed [29,30]. This feature

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of silica-stabilized microbubbles under different wetting states: (a) Wenzel state, where water penetrates the silica layer, forming a thicker and strongly bound hydration layer at the nanoscale, and (b) Cassie-Baxter state, where trapped air pockets reduce water penetration, leading to a thinner bound water layer. The thickness of this interfacial water layer plays a critical role in determining bubble hydration and stability.

observed in disordered materials, such as amorphous silica [30–32], is a characteristic low-frequency (~ 1 THz or ~ 4.2 meV) excess and indicates deviations from classical Debye behavior typical of crystalline solids. Analysis of the Bp provides insights into quasi-localized vibrational modes and structural relaxation processes that influence macroscopic material properties [33,34]. Finally, another interesting approach is the so-called elastic fixed window scan (EFWS) that is used to monitor changes in the elastic scattering intensity at a fixed energy resolution, or time window, as a function of temperature [9]. This feature provides insight into temperature-dependent variations in microscopic molecular mobility and dynamic transitions [9]. By transforming the measured signal into the mean-square displacement (MSD) of the atoms, it enables a direct measurement of the hydrogen mobility. These results can be related to macroscopic features obtained from techniques like differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) [10].

2. Materials and methods

The behavior of confined water and its role as a determining factor in the stabilization of the microbubbles was carried out in samples synthesized using three different types of silica: hydrophilic Aerosil A200 (denoted as **HPhilic**), hydrophobic Aerosil R972 (denoted as **HPhobic**), and highly hydrophobic Aerosil H15 (denoted as **H_HPhobic**). This process involves generating an oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion, stabilized by the silicas, where the water phase contains maltodextrin, a solute that solidifies upon drying, and the oil phase is volatile. Water and oil are removed from the O/W emulsion through freeze-drying, and the final product consists of the silica microbubbles in a maltodextrin matrix. Reconstituting the freeze-dried products in water leads to the formation of the desired silica-stabilized microbubbles. We hypothesize that the HPhilic surfaces induce a Wenzel-like wetting state, leading to stronger interfacial water binding and reduced mobility. In contrast, hydrophobic surfaces like the HPhobic and the H_HPhobic are expected to exhibit a Cassie-Baxter-like state, resulting in less direct water interaction with silica surfaces, increased molecular mobility, and more bulk-like water structural ordering.

2.1. Materials and sample preparation

Three types of fumed silica particles (FSPs, with >99.8 % purity) were employed in this study: hydrophilic Aerosil 200, hydrophobic Aerosil R972, (both from Evonik, Germany), slightly more hydrophobic H15 (from Wacker, Germany) and Maltodextrin glucidex 2 (with dextrose equivalent value (DE) of 2,94 % dry substance, from Roquette, France). Based on their surface properties the samples were labeled as HPhilic, HPhobic and H_HPhobic. HPhilic is synthesized using FSPs with a hydrophilic surface covered in silanol (-Si-OH) groups that can adsorb water from ambient humidity. HPhobic has hydrophobic FSPs that have been surface-treated with dimethyldichlorosilane (DDS, (CH₃)₂SiCl₂) to replace surface -OH groups with the nonpolar -Si(CH₃)₂ groups. This renders the surface hydrophobic, significantly reducing water adsorption. Finally, the H_HPhobic exhibited an even higher degree of hydrophobicity, achieved by treating silica with hexamethyldisilazane, (HMDS, (CH₃)₃SiNHSi(CH₃)₃). This reaction caps the surface with -Si(CH₃)₃ groups, resulting in a nearly fully methylated surface with minimal silanol content.

To prepare the samples an emulsion template method was used. Each formulation had 0.5 % (0.1 g) silica particles, 20 g deionized water, and 10 % (2 g) maltodextrin were mixed using a Turrax at 8000 rpm for 15 s, followed by 15 s of ultrasound treatment. Then, 10 % (w/w) cyclooctane (with 99 % purity, from Sigma-Aldrich) was added, and the mixture stirred again with the Turrax. The final powder was obtained via freeze drying. Dry samples were stored in closed containers containing bags of desiccant in order to obtain a constant relative humidity in all samples. Further details of the preparation, including the amount of water, sample composition and thermal stability are described in Ref. [10]. A

summary of these values is also provided in the supplementary information, Table S1 and Fig. S1. Micropipette aspiration was performed using borosilicate capillaries pulled and bent to a radius of 10–20 μm . The pipette was connected to a piezoelectric pressure controller, with zero pressure calibrated before each experiment. Bubbles were loaded into a 1 mm sealed chamber, contacted with the pipette, and aspirated under constant negative pressure (ΔP), followed by pressure release to monitor relaxation. Critical pressure (ΔP_c) was determined by stepwise pressure increase until the bubble began to enter the pipette. Bright-field imaging was conducted at 0.1–1 s interval [16]. For neutron scattering experiments, approximately 450 mg of each silica Pickering particle and 0.9 g of maltodextrin (TOSCA, only) were distributed in an aluminum foil envelope, placed in a flat aluminum holder, sealed with indium wire, and stored at room temperature. The dry powder was gently ground using a mortar and pestle to avoid disrupting the silica shell structure. All the neutron experiments are carried out once in large scale facilities.

2.2. Neutron spectroscopy

Variations in wettability results in distinct water networks along the interface, leading to water mobility occurring at different timescales. Therefore, in this study it was essential to combine three neutron spectrometers: TOSCA, an inelastic neutron scattering (INS) spectrometer located at the ISIS Facility of the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory in the UK, which provides information on molecular vibrations over a broad energy range corresponding to the fs timescale; FOCUS, a time-of-flight spectrometer operated at the Paul Scherrer Institute in Villigen, Switzerland, used to detect the low-frequency vibrational density of states of water dynamics in the ps regime; and EMU, a neutron back-scattering spectrometer at ANSTO, Lucas Heights, Australia, offering insights into thermal activation observable between $0.15 \text{ ns} < \tau < 4.5 \text{ ns}$ [35].

TOSCA is an indirect geometry time-of-flight neutron spectrometer with a spectral resolution of approximately 1.5 % [36]. The time-of-flight INS spectra were recorded in both back-scattering and forward-scattering geometries, which were subsequently combined to obtain the hydrogen-projected vibrational density of states (VDOS). The typical measurement duration varied between 2 and 6 h, depending on the hydrogen content of the sample. Data for all samples were collected at 10 K and reduced using Mantid [37–39]. The signal from an empty aluminum cell was subtracted. Subsequently, based on our previous work reporting maltodextrin content in the dry samples (approximately 70 % of the total mass), [10] the INS spectra of pure maltodextrin were re-scaled accordingly and subtracted from the spectra of the Pickering particles. This processing step ensures that the resulting spectra are primarily dominated by the signal from water in the samples. Table S2 in the supplementary information gives the masses of all samples measured.

FOCUS is a direct geometry neutron time-of-flight spectrometer with variable elastic energy resolution. Here measurements have been performed with an incident wavelength of $\lambda = 4 \text{ \AA}$, covering a Q-range between $0.3 \text{ \AA}^{-1} < Q < 1.8 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ and ΔE of $\sim 200 \text{ \mu eV}$, approximately 20 ps, obtained by measuring the sample HPhilic at $T = 50 \text{ K}$ where the signal is fully elastic. All samples were measured at 300 K, 250 K, 175 K, 100 K and no quasi-elastic (QE) broadening was observed. For data reduction and processing (conversion of TOF to energy transfer, normalization to a vanadium standard, empty cell subtraction), the program LAMP was used [40]. In this work only the data at 100 K was analyzed because of the better statistics.

Slower motions were probed by the EMU backscattering spectrometer with a neutron wavelength of $\lambda = 6.28 \text{ \AA}$, also covering a Q-range between $0.3 < Q < 1.9 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, an energy resolution of 1.1 μeV and a dynamic range from -28 to 28 \mu eV [41]. QENS measurements were obtained at 300 K and EFWS performed from 300 to 50 K for cooling and from 50 to 300 K for heating. Results for the EFWS are shown in Supplementary information Fig. S2. The heating rate was approximately 1

K/min. To minimize thermal gradients across the sample, an aluminum heat shield was attached to the sample can. Subtraction of empty can, normalization for neutron flux and calibration with vanadium for detector efficiency and solid angle was performed using a Mathematica script. Here QE signal was analyzed and shown in Supplementary information Fig. S3. The results show no broadening, indicating that the relaxation processes of the dynamics determining the MSD are too slow to be detected from the resolution of the instrument. The evolution of the elastic intensity as a function of temperature was analyzed to extract the mean square displacements (MSDs, $\langle u^2 \rangle$) using the Gaussian approximation [42]. This step allowed determining “dynamical transitions”, characterized by a deviation of $\langle u^2 \rangle$ vs T from the Debye-Waller behavior, and in turn the onset of anharmonic motions.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Verifying the formation of bubbles using micropipette aspiration

Micropipette aspiration was used to verify the air-in-water structure of the microbubbles. Fig. 2 shows the aspiration and bursting of a microbubble. From the data, it is possible to verify a gas-looking substance coming out from the particle-stabilized bubbles as well as the collapse of the structures/shells. The observed burst is shown in the supplementary information, movie S1.

3.2. Hydrogen bonding strength and water vibrational stiffness

Due to hydrogen’s exceptionally large incoherent neutron scattering cross section (σ_H), which is at least an order of magnitude greater than that of most other elements typically found in biological systems, [43] the measured scattering intensity, $S(Q, \omega)$, is dominated by the dynamic behavior of the hydrogen atoms. In its simplified form, the INS signal primarily reflects self-correlated atomic motions, [44] and can be expressed from eq. (1):

$$S(q, n\omega_i) \propto (q \cdot U_i)^2 e^{-[q \cdot \omega_{tot}]^2} \ast \sigma_H \quad (1)$$

here, U_i represents the zero-point displacement of a hydrogen atom associated with vibrational mode ω_i , and $n = 1$ is the fundamental frequency. ω_{total} corresponds to the cumulative displacement due to all vibrational modes. The exponential term, known as the Debye-Waller factor, reflects molecular flexibility: lower atomic mobility corresponds to smaller mean-square displacements (MSD), and while higher mobility results in larger MSD values [45].

Fig. 3 presents a comparison of inelastic neutron scattering (INS) spectra, measured using TOSCA, for bulk water and water confined within various silica particles, offering insights into the dynamic behavior and vibrational characteristics of the samples. Turning to the analysis of the peak positions, the reference spectrum of bulk water (black line, in Fig. 3 a, b, c) shows two clear features [46]. The first is a very sharp vibrational mode centered at about 50 cm^{-1} . The second is

associated with the librational band that is categorized as rocking (R), wagging (W) and twisting (T) modes representing hindered rotations and shows a sharp edge around 450 cm^{-1} for pure water. Confinement effects are confirmed by the blue shift of the 50 cm^{-1} water peak, which is now observed around 80 cm^{-1} in the Pickering particles [47,48]. Moreover, a comparison of vibrational intensities reveals that the attenuation (or damping) of this mode is less pronounced in the hydrophobic H_{HP}hobic sample. This suggests that, despite being confined, the water molecules retain a higher degree of mobility. Here, the hydrophobic nature of this particular silica matrix appears to reduce the interaction between the water molecules and the interface, allowing the water to remain more dynamically unrestricted when compared to the other two samples. This behavior can be interpreted through the lens of recent entropy-focused studies, presented by Havenith and co-workers, [49] which introduces the concept of an entropy-driven competition between confined and free water populations. In this model, water molecules that are released from tightly bound interfacial regions into the bulk or less structured environments experience an increase in configurational entropy, which can thermodynamically favor structural transitions. This release leads to entropy gain, since the water is ‘freed’ from tight interfacial binding and can explore a larger volume. Here, this correlates with the higher INS intensity (Fig. 3c) representing more mobile hydrogen atoms in the H_{HP}hobic. Additionally, the lower enthalpy observed in H_{HP}hobic when compared to the other samples using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) [10], 300 J/g for H_{PH}ilic versus 250 J/g for H_{PH}obic and 210 J/g for the H_{HP}hobic, reflects reduced hydrogen bonding density or weaker surface interactions, which in turn facilitates the release or dynamic loosening of hydration water. Conversely, the higher enthalpy values of H_{PH}ilic and H_{PH}obic suggest stronger silica–water interactions, leading to tighter hydration shells, and therefore reduced entropy in the confined phase. This further explains the reduced vibrational intensity around the 80 cm^{-1} peaks, (Fig. 3a, b).

Furthermore, changes in the librational water band ($750\text{--}1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) are also remarkable. Similar to what has been observed in other systems using neutron spectroscopy, bound water restricts the librational motions, causing this band to soften, weaken, or disappear [50]. Here the observed red shift corroborates with the idea of changes in the hydrogen-bond network, mostly for the H_{PH}ilic. In this sample, the hydrophilic nature of the FSPs induces stronger bonds, effectively locking the water molecules, removing their librational freedom and thus greatly diminishing (or even cancelling) the librational band.

As illustrated in Fig. 3a, the hydrophilic silica, whose surface contains a high density of silanol (-Si-OH) groups, shows a greater reduction of the librational band. This effect is fully consistent with the higher enthalpy observed in these samples and is a clear consequence of the formation of strong hydrogen bonds. Additionally, based on previous evolved gas analysis (EGA) the delayed water loss on the BS_{A200}, observed at $73 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ compared to around $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in H_{HP}hobic and $65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ H_{PH}obic by [10], is yet another proof of a different organization of interfacial water molecules induced by its specific affinity to the A200

Fig. 2. Micropipette aspiration shows the formation of the microbubbles (dark shell represents the silica particles and the white the trapped gas) in aqueous solution.

Fig. 3. Inelastic neutron scattering spectra ($S(q,\omega)$) for bulk water (black curve) versus water confined in (A) HPhylic, (B) HPhobic and (C) H_HPhobic. All spectra were recorded at the temperature of 10 K. For better visualization the x-axis is discontinuous, with a break between 120 and 360 break between cm^{-1} . Note that the measured total spectra of the Pickering particles were subtracted from the re-scaled spectra of maltodextrin leading to the observation of the water response only. The confined water exhibits a broad, down-shifted librational band ($\sim 400\text{--}800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) as well as a shift of the vibrational mode from approximately 50 to 80 cm^{-1} . To convert wavenumbers to energy we divide by 8.

surface. In this case, the distortion of the tetrahedral organization of interfacial water molecules creates a new type of relaxation process reflected by the observation of a quasi-elastic signal in the neutron spectra using a time resolution of 0.5 ns [10]. The water in HPhobic is less distorted than in the other samples suggesting that the surrounding environment has a smaller impact on its structure. For this FSP the water molecules keep their bulk-like structure, indicating that the matrix does not heavily alter the water hydrogen-bond network. This suggests a kind of intermediate behavior with some confinement, but minimal structural perturbation. In conclusion, based on the vibrational mode analysis together with input from DSC and EGA data, water is more constrained in the HPhylic which hydrophilic surface is covered in silanol (Si-OH) groups.

3.3. Localized vibrational motions and structural rigidity

Relaxation processes occur when molecules undergo reorientations, diffusions, or structural rearrangements, and in a QENS experiment this translates to the broadening of the elastic line. As such signal was not detected in the samples studied here using the FOCUS spectrometer, molecular motions of water in the FSP network remain largely harmonic within $\sim 10^{-11}\text{--}10^{-12}$ s timescale. However, the evaluation of the vibrational density of states (VDOS) shows a clear Bp at 100 K. This excess of low-energy vibrational modes, seen as an asymmetric peak in the low-energy region in Fig. 4 a, b, c, is linked to structural disorder in amorphous systems. It typically represents collective vibrational states related to the structural heterogeneities of the silica micro-particles. To evaluate the Bp position and intensity, the spectra at 100 K were fitted by the eq. (2) [51–54]:

$$g(\omega) = \frac{A}{\omega^2 + \omega_0^2} + B \exp \left[-\frac{\left(\ln \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_{Bp}} \right) \right)^2}{2W^2} \right] \quad (2)$$

where ω is the energy transfer and $g(\omega)$ is the intensity of the neutrons measured with that energy transfer. The first term describes the QENS contribution approximated by a Lorentzian function with width ω_0 (half width of half maximum) and amplitude A . The second term accounts for the Bp in terms of a lognormal function of width W , and B and ω_{Bp} are the intensity and the position of the Bp, respectively. The data fitting was performed in an energy range from 1 to 10 meV.

From the fitting parameters we obtain a slightly higher ω_{Bp} for the H_HPhobic, $5.8 \pm 0.1 \text{ meV}$ vs $5.3 \pm 0.1 \text{ meV}$ for the HPhylic and $5.4 \pm 0.1 \text{ meV}$ for the HPhobic. This indicates that hydrophobicity significantly enhances the structural rigidity of the silica-hydrogen network, while hydrophilicity contributes to flexibility and disorder. This assumption is further supported by the values of the Bp width (W) that is equals to $0.60 \pm 0.05 \text{ meV}$, $0.90 \pm 0.06 \text{ meV}$ and $0.98 \pm 0.06 \text{ meV}$ for H_HPhobic, HPhylic, and HPhobic respectively. The smallest width observed for the H_HPhobic can be understood as a consequence of a more rigid structure. This will facilitate water mobility as also indicated by the INS data.

3.4. Temperature-dependent water mobility

Elastic fixed window scans (EFWS) are commonly used as starting points for neutron backscattering experiments to quickly understand system dynamics as well as to determine the temperature-dependent

Fig. 4. Vibrational density of states ($g(\omega)$) as a function of energy transfer (meV) for the (A) HPhylic, (B) HPhobic and (C) H_HPhobic at the temperature of 100 K measured on the FOCUS instrument at PSI.

mean-square displacement (MSD, $\langle u^2(T) \rangle$) using the Gaussian approximation [42]. In a purely harmonic system, the MSD can be described by the quantum Debye model using the eq. (3): [55,56].

$$\langle u^2(T) \rangle = \frac{3h^2}{4\pi^2 m k_B \Theta_D} \left[\phi\left(\frac{\Theta_D}{T}\right) + \frac{1}{4} \frac{\Theta_D}{T} \right] \quad (3)$$

where h is Planck's constant, k_B is Boltzmann's constant, and $\phi(x)$ is the Debye integral $\phi(x) = \int_0^x \frac{t}{e^t - 1} dt$. This expression incorporates both the zero-point displacement (the $1/4$ term as $T \rightarrow 0$) and the full quantum statistics of a Debye spectrum of phonons. The atomic mass, m , corresponds to the predominant scattering species (in practice, the effective mass of the H-containing groups). When analyzing the data using Eq. 3, the only adjustable parameter in the fit is the Debye temperature Θ_D of the vibrational spectrum. The least-squares fit of the above expression to the experimental $\langle u^2(T) \rangle$ was performed up to the onset of systematic deviations.

The extracted MSD from the EMU experiments together with the fit results are shown in Fig. 5. Good fits were obtained in the low-T range, yielding effective Debye temperatures, which characterizes the harmonic behavior of the Pickering particle, equal to 460 K for H_{HP}hobic which indicates less water binding in the surface, 490 K for H_{PH}ilic and 560 K for H_{PH}obic. This difference further highlights the influence of the surface chemistry in the water vibrational stiffness [57,58]. Furthermore, the deviation of the experimental data from the fitted curve indicates the onset temperature of anharmonic or relaxational dynamics. This response is observed at 210 K for the hydrophobic H_{PH}obic, at 225 K for the highly hydrophobic H_HPHobic and at 250 K for the hydrophilic H_{PH}ilic. Since no QE was observed, we can argue that in the nanosecond time scale the observed dynamical transitions are related to the rotational dynamics of the nonpolar -Si(CH₃)₂ groups at the surface of H_{PH}obic which are unlocked at the lowest temperature, followed by the activation of the surface groups -Si(CH₃) in H_HPHobic and finally the Si-OH groups in the hydrophilic A200. Moreover, the reduced surface-water interaction leads to the higher MSD in H_HPHobic in agreement with the INS, the width of the B_p and the DSC data. On the other hand, H_{PH}ilic and H_{PH}obic show similar MSD values, a behavior already detected when analyzing the B_p width and in agreement with the similar values of the B_p width (W) and position ω_{Bp} . This further corroborates the idea that the mechanical rigidity is comparable for these samples, but highest for the H_HPHobic.

3.5. Surface chemistry determines wetting states

The observed differences can be attributed to the complex surface chemistry of the Pickering particles and the extent of the water adsorption at their surfaces. This hydration environment is associated with differences in water mobility and interfacial structure.

In general, when rough, methylated particles reside at microbubble interfaces, the presence of air pockets enable water to circumvent direct

confinement. As a result, the interfacial water layer becomes thin or discontinuous, exhibiting bulk-like mobility and reduced structural ordering. This configuration leads to a decrease in interfacial enthalpy. In contrast, hydrophilic particles promote the formation of a continuous, strongly bound hydration layer—analogue to a Wenzel state—where water molecules are tightly associated with the surface. This results in reduced molecular mobility and an increase in interfacial enthalpy.

In the case of H_{PH}ilic, its surface being covered by Si-OH will facilitate the formation of strongly hydrogen-bonded water. Essentially, the hydrogen-bond network acts as a soft glue, where the intermediate Debye temperature value results from this flexible and dissipative hydration layer. On heating, some of the water molecules gain enough energy to break free from the surface, hydrogen bonds break, and water mobility occurs, leading to deviation from the Debye model. This yields a hydration environment with strong hydrogen bonding and reduced water mobility, similar to a Wenzel wetting state.

On the other hand, the methyl-terminated H_{PH}obic exhibits reduced water adsorption and increased water mobility, consistent with a less strongly bound interfacial water layer that resembles a partially wetted Cassie-Baxter state. This occurs because the sample adsorbs less than a monolayer of water, and any residual silanol group might form strong H-bonds with the water molecules, making these water molecules extremely localized, almost immobile. This is reflected by the highest value of the Debye temperature and higher water vibrational stiffness – the smallest intensity in Fig. 3 – leading to a smaller total entropy. Furthermore, even if the surface -CH₃ groups attached to the silica undergo slow rotational motions that can be detected at the time window of EMU [42], this motion is expected to be strongly hindered since this methylated surface acts like a “dynamically stiff” environment and lacks the fluid-like layer present in A200. This explains the overall smaller MSD observed for hydrogen.

Finally, H_HPHobic has numerous methyl hydrogens attached to the surface via flexible Si-O-Si(CH₃)₃ linkages that will also contribute to the measured incoherent signal. As the temperature approaches ambient, the motions of the methyl groups can explore a larger angular space, contributing to a large MSD. The surface behaves like a soft, rubbery organic layer with few constraints, lacking any rigid hydrogen-bond network. This results in the highest observed mobility among the Pickering particles and the lowest enthalpy. Thus, H_HPHobic is the softest dynamically because its surface chemistry provides the least resistance to motion and yields higher mobility and entropy [49]. This is analogous to a Cassie-Baxter state.

These trends align with general observations that water at hydrophilic interfaces forms tight layers (involving multiple hydrogen bonds), whereas water on hydrophobic surfaces is only weakly attached to the surface, resulting in very different dynamical behaviors of the interface. The presence of strong surface hydrogen bonds (hydrophilic case) increases the effective “stiffness” of the interface until those bonds are broken, whereas a hydrophobic, methylated interface presents a more “floppy” environment where motions can occur with less resistance.

Fig. 5. Mean square displacements for all samples as a function of temperature. The square open boxes represent experimental data and solid lines the fitted curve using the Debye model described by Eq. 3.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we investigated how the surface hydrophobicity of fumed silica particles (FSPs) influences the dynamics of interfacial water across a broad temporal range, from tenths of fs to few ns. By integrating wetting theory with the experimental data, we propose a novel framework for describing the interfacial water behavior for three silica microbubbles ranging from hydrophilic to highly hydrophobic. In the hydrophilic regime, water exhibits characteristics consistent with a Wenzel wetting state with a rigid interfacial water layer. In contrast, the moderately hydrophobic sample approximates a Cassie–Baxter-like configuration, characterized by reduced surface –OH groups and diminished water adsorption. Water molecules adjacent to these methylated domains cannot hydrogen-bond to the surface and thus enter a “frustrated” state. Two pathways may account for this frustration: (i) under confinement, water molecules may organize into hydrogen-bonded clusters, resulting in enthalpy-driven attraction as proposed by Li et al. [28]; or (ii) under dewetting conditions, frustrated water molecules are expelled from the interface, leaving behind bulk-like domains with enhanced molecular mobility. Finally, the highly hydrophobic sample, with an almost fully methylated surface, has the most dynamically free interface, being also in the Cassie–Baxter like state. These findings are consistent with established interfacial hydration principles: water at hydrophilic interfaces tends to form tightly bound layers involving multiple hydrogen bonds, whereas water at hydrophobic interfaces remains only weakly attached, resulting in very different dynamical behaviors. Strong hydrogen bonding at hydrophilic interfaces increases the effective “stiffness” of the interface until those bonds are broken, whereas hydrophobic surfaces create a more “floppy” environment where motions can occur with less resistance.

To our knowledge, neutron spectroscopy has not yet been applied to study the wetting of Pickering particles at interfaces. From the brief overview given in Table 1, which compares the benefits and drawbacks of the use of neutrons to other techniques normally used in the study of Pickering particles, we argue that neutron scattering can be a valuable addition to the existing toolbox. The specific advantage of this non-destructive technique is that it provides information about the dynamics of water molecules. In principle, from the quasielastic neutron scattering (QENS) data, it is possible to extract the diffusion coefficient at the interface between a fluid and a solid surface and quantify the fraction of mobile water molecules. From these values and using the definition given by Wang et al. [6], we can estimate macroscopic parameters that affects wettability, i.e. contact angle. However, to further establish the proposed approach in this field more research is needed, i. e. studying different Particle-stabilized systems. This study will be possible with new instrumentation and in particular with the MIRACLES backscattering spectrometer [59].

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Charalampos Tsekeridis: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Svemir Rudić:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Investigation, Data curation. **Alice Klapproth:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Investigation, Data curation. **Unique Gyanu Yogi:** Writing – review & editing, Software. **Albert T. Poortinga:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Heloisa N. Bordallo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Table 1

Comparison of the advantages and disadvantages of conventional techniques to characterize the properties of Pickering particles at interfaces with that of neutron spectroscopy.

Technique	Advantages	Disadvantages ¹
Contact angle measurements; for an overview of different contact angle measuring techniques [4]	Well-established parameter determining the stability of Pickering-stabilized systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not in situ • Generally, very laborious
Interfacial rheology [60]	Clearly established link exists between measured properties and stability of Pickering-stabilized systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not in situ
Imaging of adsorbed particles [5]	Gives an actual (microscopic) image of the interface <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gives information about the wetting of adsorbed particles, one of the most important parameters determining the stability of Pickering-stabilized systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not in situ • Generally, only qualitative information
Neutron spectroscopy (this work)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not only static information but also information about the dynamics of adsorbed water • In situ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does not (yet) give a value for the diffusion coefficient, that can be related to the contact angle through Gibbs energy. • Expensive, requires equipment that is not widely available

¹ A disadvantage of all techniques is that they measure only part of the large set of parameters determining the stability and behavior of Particle-stabilized systems, i.e. for a complete understanding, multiple techniques must be combined.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Charalampos Tsekeridis reports financial support was provided by European Union. Heloisa Nunes Bordallo reports financial support was provided by Carlsberg Foundation. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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